

15th EUROPEAN GEOPARKS CONFERENCE

Natural Park Sierra Norte de Sevilla

UNESCO Global Geopark

*Geoparks: memory of Earth,
future for People*

JUNTA DE ANDALUCÍA
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, GANADERÍA,
PESCA Y DESARROLLO SOSTENIBLE

Ginesu S. & Capula M.	EXAMPLES OF POLYCYCLIC INTRUSIONS IN GRANITIC MAGMAS IN SARDINIA (ITALY, WESTERN MEDITERRANEAN SEA): SOME GEOMORPHOLOGIC CONSIDERATIONS	152
Patrocínio, F, Castro, E., Loureiro F., Gomes H.	THE INTERPRETIVE PANELS OF THE ESTRELA GEOPARK AS A TOOL FOR THE PROMOTION OF GEOLOGICAL HERITAGE	153
Joao Castel-Branco	THE GREAT ROUTE OF THE ESTRELA GEOPARK AS A PROMOTION FOR NATURE TOURISM	154
Azevedo, P. & Castro, E.	THE ESTRELA GEOPARK TOURIST PARTNERS NETWORK AS A SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY	155
Vittorio, Orrù, Angelo, Naseddu, Sergio, Ginesu, Giuseppina, Gradoli & Stefania, Sias	GEOMORFOLOGICAL EVIDENCE OF THE RECENT EVOLUTION OF SAN GIOVANNI CAVE (DOMUSNOVAS, SOUTHWESTERN SARDINIA, ITALY) IN THE PARCO GEOMINERARIO DELLA SARDEGNA	156
José Caro-Gómez, Antonio Díaz del Olmo, Fernando Álvarez-García, Genaro Borja-Barrera, José Manuel César Recio-Espejo & Alberto Gil-Toja	GEOSITES OF HISTORICAL AND NATURAL HERITAGE FROM THE SIERRA NORTE GEOPARK (SPAIN): CAREQ, RESEARCH AND A PROPOSAL OF SPZ MANAGEMENT	157
Jonathan Carter, Peter Chowne & Georgina Bois	THE ASPIRING JERSEY GEOPARK	158
Mikko Kiuttu, HelenaTukiainen, Risto Kalliola, Janne Alahuhta & Jan Hjort	LANDFORMS CONTRIBUTE TO PLANT BIODIVERSITY IN ROKUA GLOBAL GEOPARK, FINLAND	159
Thierry Pélissié & Maéva Orliac	DEADENDER: USE FOSSILS TO EXPLORE THE PROCESS OF BIOLOGICAL EXTINCTION IN CAUSSES DU QUERCY GEOPARK	160
Esquinca-Cano, F., Avendaño-Gil, M. J., Poch, J. & Gil-Ríos, A.	IMPLEMENTATION OF THE GEOPARK MODEL BASED ON THE ECORREGIONS IN THE STATE OF CHIAPAS (MEXICO)	161
Almudena Leal Santamaría; Javier Hernández-Blanco; Javier Fernández-Lozano & Jaime Bonachea Pico	VALLEYS OF CANTABRIA ASPIRING UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK	162
Santagati, S.; Ortolano, G., Palermi, A.S., Tralongo, S., Parisi, C., Cirrincione, R.	ASPRMONTE GEOPARK PROJECT: COMMUNICATION AND SCIENTIFIC DIVULGATION OF A UNIQUE GEOLOGICAL HERITAGE	163
Peter Chowne & Anne Chowne	JERSEY ROCKS: FROM AN ARTIST'S PERSPECTIVE	164
Schilling, M. & Herrera, P.	KÜTRALKURA UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK FOR THE SUSTAINABLE LOCAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE ARAUCANIA REGION, CHILE	165
Rocha, Daniela, Bastos, Susana, Alexandre, Luís Alexandre	GEOEDUCATION IN ACTION IN THE AROUCA UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK: THE «ILLUSTRATE YOUR SCHOOL» EDUCATIONAL PROJECT	166
Cristiane Gomes; Marcos Nascimento & Nayara Silva	SERIDÓ GEOPARK PROJECT PROMOTING REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN RIO GRANDE DO NORTE, BRAZIL	167
Patricia Herrera	RURAL WELL-BEING: KEY TO AN INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN THE FUTURE OF GEOPARK GLOBAL UNESCO KUTRALKURA OF CHILE	168

VALLEYS OF CANTABRIA ASPIRING UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK

*Leal Santamaría, Almudena ¹; Hernández-Blanco, Javier ²; Fernández-Lozano, Javier ³;
Bonachea Pico, Jaime ⁴

¹ Mancomunidad de Municipios Sostenibles de Cantabria, Edificio de la Lonja, Puerta A, 2º Izq. Santoña, SPAIN. proyectos@municipiossostenibles.com

² Mancomunidad de Municipios Sostenibles de Cantabria, Edificio de la Lonja, Puerta A, 2º Izq. Santoña, SPAIN. hernandez-j@municipiossostenibles.com

³ Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Cantabria, Av. Los Castros s/n, Santander, SPAIN.
j.fernandezlozano@unican.es

⁴ Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Cantabria, Av. Los Castros s/n, Santander, SPAIN.
jaime.bonachea@unican.es

Keywords: Aspiring Geopark, Geotourism, Sustainable development, Cantabria region.

The Atlantic Geoparks project, funded by the Interreg Atlantic area programme, aims to highlight the Geoparks of the Atlantic area. This Spanish candidacy consider the declaration of a geopark in Cantabria region, called Valleys of Cantabria (Asón, Miera and Soba). The territory covered is about 800 km², including 20 municipalities and more than 61,000 inhabitants. A database including more than 50 geosites, natural elements and cultural points of interest has been constructed. These geosites are based on criteria as type of interest, intrinsic or scientific value, potential of use, presence of other complementary values or existence of protection figures. Among others, coastal and aeolian, karst and glaciers landscapes can be found, as well as other stratigraphic, tectonic, and paleontological features.

The coastal area of the geopark concentrates a high diversity of environments highly representative of littoral zones of medium latitudes. Barchan and longitudinal dunes in an orthogonal framework climbing the mountainside constitute the relevant dune system of Sonabia. There are also numerous peat bogs with ages ranging from 10,000 years B.P. and 2,000-5,000 years B.P. The fossil forest of Trengandín beach indicates that between 2,890-4,070 years B.P. the sea level was at least 2 m below the current one. The Asón area is internationally recognized for its varied and rich underground heritage with more than 4,000 caves explored. Some of these caves have been used as shelters, at least, during the last 45,000 years (remains paintings of Covalanas cave, World Heritage of UNESCO, have been dated in about 20,000 years). The maximum glacial development of this area occurred between 44,000 and 29,000 years B.P. Glacial remains appear at levels around 600 a.s.l., the lowest of the Iberian Peninsula. The declaration of a geopark constitutes a great opportunity to promote the geotourism and development of the territory. Geopark contributes to the 2030 sustainable development goals in the territory. Development through sustainable geotourism is one of the key pillars of Valleys of Cantabria aspiring Geopark. It will create job opportunities for the local communities through tourism, but also through the promotion of local culture and products. Also, it will aim to give local people a sense of pride in their region and strengthen the identification with the area. In addition, local communities and visitors learn to live in harmony with nature. Finally, it will improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning.

VALLEYS OF CANTABRIA ASPIRING UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK

Leal Santamaría, Almudena; Hernández-Blanco, Javier; Fernández-Lozano, Javier; Bonachea Pico, Jaime

Mancomunidad de Municipios Sostenibles de Cantabria, Edificio de la Lonja, Puerta A, 2º Izq. Santoña, SPAIN. hernandez-j@municiiosostenibles.com
 Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Cantabria, Av. Los Castros s/n, Santander, SPAIN. jaime.bonachea@unican.es

INTRODUCTION

The Atlantic Geoparks project, funded by the Interreg Atlantic area programme, aims to highlight the Geoparks of the Atlantic area. This Spanish candidacy considers the declaration of a geopark in Cantabria region, called Valleys of Cantabria (Asón, Miera and Soba). The territory covered is about 800 km², including 20 municipalities and more than 61,000 inhabitants.

MAIN GOALS

Promote and disseminate the natural and cultural heritage of the UNESCO World Geoparks, in order to contribute to the economic development of the territory. Promote the declaration of new geoparks, in this case, **Valleys of Cantabria Geopark**.

Different geomorphological landscapes and more than 50 geosites

Inventory of Geological heritage

High diversity of environments

Inventory of Natural heritage

Economic Development and Geotourism

The declaration of a geopark constitutes a great opportunity to promote the geotourism and development of the territory. Valleys of Cantabria Global Geopark will create job opportunities for the local communities through tourism, but also through the promotion of local culture and products. It will improve education, awareness-raising and human and institutional capacity on climate change mitigation, adaptation, impact reduction and early warning.

A rich architectural and cultural heritage

Inventory of Cultural heritage

Acknowledgments: This work has been possible thanks to the financing of the Atlantic Geoparks project (EAPA_250 / 2016), Interreg Atlantic Space Program through the European Regional Development Fund.